

Synthesis, structural elucidation and biocidal aspects of some alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

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Abstract : Alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} having N₂S₂ potential donors, of the general formula, [M(L){S₂P^O₂G₂}] (where L = macrocyclic ligands L₁, L₂, L₃, L₄ and L₅, M = Zn^{II} and

Cd^{II} and G = (CH₃)₂C-CH₂CH(CH₃), (CH₃)₂C-C(CH₃)₂, H₂C.C(CH₃)₂CH₂, H₂C.C(C₂H₅)₂CH₂ and CH₃-CH-CH-CH₃ have been synthesized from the reactions of [M(L)X₂] (where M = Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} and X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ or CH₃COO⁻) with ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates in 1 : 2 molar ratio in THF. These compounds have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, molecular weight determination, IR, ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR. Molecular weight determinations of these complexes indicate their monomeric nature. Octahedral structure has been proposed on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR. Antimicrobial activities of these derivatives have been studied by screening them against fungi, such as *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Trichoderma harzianum* and bacteria, such as *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives were found to be more fungitoxic and antibacterial than their corresponding macrocyclic complexes.

Keywords : Alkylene dithiophosphates, macrocyclic complexes, mixed ligand complexes, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}.

Introduction

The chemistry of macrocyclic ligands is a fascinating area of intense study for inorganic chemists. The possibility to tailor-make different types of macrocycles for specific use has promoted much of this interest. Among others, these include for biological systems, therapeutic reagents for the treatment of metal intoxication, synthetic ionophores and the selective extraction of heavy and precious metals¹⁻⁴. In spite of vast innovation in macrocyclic chemistry and tremendous interest in mixed ligand complexes, no mixed ligand macrocyclic complex was reported till our publications. Alkylene dithiophosphates has been the area of our thrust since last 3 decades⁵⁻¹⁴. Considering the importance of mixed ligand macrocyclic complexes, we reported synthesis, characterization, biocidal and catalytic aspects of mixed ligand macrocyclic complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II} with dialkyl-

and alkylene dithiophosphates having N₂S₂ potential donors in 14 to 20 membered rings¹⁵⁻²⁶. Considering the interesting results obtained during the course of above investigations it was, therefore, planned to extend the above work on main group metals also. Recently we have reported the synthesis, characterization and biocidal aspects of dialkyl dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Pb^{II}¹⁸⁻²⁰. In continuation to the above work we hereby report the synthesis, characterization and biocidal aspects of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Pb^{II} having N₂S₂ potential donors in 14 to 20 membered rings.

Results and discussion

Zinc and cadmium salts react with *o*-aminothiophenol and dicarboxylic acids in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios in methanol to afford white or off white and yellow complexes as shown below :

Scheme 1

X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ or CH₃COO⁻ and L = L¹, L², L³, L⁴, L⁵
 n = 1, 2, 3, 4 or (CH₂)_n = *o*-C₆H₄⁻, M = Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

Fig. 1. Tentative structure of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}.

L₁ = Macrocyclic ligand derived from *o*-aminothiophenol and malonic acid (n = 1); {Dibenzo[6,7,13,14]-[5,12]diazia[1,8]dithiacyclotetradeca[2,4,9,11]tetraone}*
 L₂ = Macrocyclic ligand derived from *o*-aminothiophenol and succinic acid (n = 2); {Dibenzo[7,8,15,16]-[6,14]diazia[1,9]dithiacyclohexadeca[2,5,10,13]tetraone}*
 L₃ = Macrocyclic ligand derived from *o*-aminothiophenol and glutaric acid (n = 3); {Dibenzo[8,9,17,18]-[7,16]diazia[1,10]dithiacyclooctadeca[2,6,11,15]tetraone}*
 L₄ = Macrocyclic ligand derived from *o*-aminothiophenol and adipic acid (n = 4); {Dibenzo[9,10,19,20]-[8,18]diazia[1,11]dithiacycloicososa[2,7,12,17]tetraone}*
 L₅ = Macrocyclic ligand derived from *o*-aminothiophenol and phthalic acid (CH₂)_n = *o*-C₆H₄⁻; {Tetrabenzo[3,4,7,8,11,12,15,16][6,14]diazia[1,9]dithiacyclohexadeca[2,5,10,13]tetraone}*
 (*IUPAC names have been mentioned in parenthesis)

The above macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in THF react with methanolic solution of ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates in 1 : 2 molar ratios to afford alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} macrocyclic complexes in the following manner :

Scheme 2

The symbols of the alkylene dithiophosphate anions, of their ammonium salts, used for the synthesis of mixed ligand macrocyclic complexes have been depicted by a-e through the script.

Except THF and DMSO, these derivatives are insoluble in almost all organic solvents. All Zn^{II} complexes are light yellow, yellow, off-white in colour and Cd^{II} complexes are white, off-white, pale yellow, yellow in colour. All Zn^{II} complexes melt in the temperature range 186–200 °C and Cd^{II} complexes melt in the temperature range 200–224 °C. The molar conductance of 10⁻³ M solutions in DMSO lies in the range 3–10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, showing that these complexes are non-electrolyte. The molecular weight determinations indicate their monomeric nature.

Infrared spectra :

In the macrocyclic complexes, the four bands in the region 1680–1570(s), 1590–1535(m), 1285–1255(s) and 690–642(w) cm⁻¹ have been ascribed to the amide I, amide II, amide III and amide IV in-plane deformation vibrations respectively²⁸. A broad band in the region 3280–3178(m) cm⁻¹ has been assigned to the ν(N–H) vibration

of the secondary amino group. These bands do not show any significant change from their parent macrocyclic complexes. Two bands present in the region 1080–1045 cm^{-1} and 895–860 cm^{-1} may be assigned to (P)–O–C and P–O–(C) stretching vibrations, respectively²⁹. The band present between 1000–945 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the ring vibrations of dioxaphospholanes and dioxaphosphorinanes respectively, which are probably coupled with C–C stretching vibrations^{30,31}. A weak band present in the region 585–538 cm^{-1} has been attributed to P–S symmetric and asymmetric vibrations. A strong band observed in the region 755–675 cm^{-1} , which also appears in ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates at around the same region, is attributed to the P=S moiety. This indicates the unidentate behavior of the dithiophosphate moieties. The presence of sharp and weak bands in the region 580–448 cm^{-1} and 385–325 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(\text{M–N})$ and $\nu(\text{M–S})$ vibrations, respectively^{8,32}.

¹H NMR spectral data :

The structure of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been further confirmed by recording the ¹H NMR using DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. In addition to the protons appear in the parent macrocyclic complexes, the additional protons of alkylene dithiophosphates moieties appears in the spectra. The methyl protons of tetramethylethylene moiety, butylene dithiophosphate moiety and neo-pentylene dithiophosphate moiety appeared in the range δ 1.38 to 1.56 ppm. The protons of methylene and methine moieties appear in the range δ 3.8 to 4.9 ppm. The broad singlet observed between δ 8.18 to 8.56 ppm has been assigned the proton of -C(O)NH- group. The protons of -CH₂- group of malonic acid appear as a singlet in the range, δ 3.04 to 3.29 ppm. The methylene protons of -CH₂-CH₂- group of succinic acid appear as a singlet in the range of δ 3.30 to 3.36 ppm. The protons of α -C atoms of glutaric acid moiety were observed as a multiplet δ 3.14 to 3.16 ppm. The protons of β -C atoms of the above moiety appeared as a multiplet δ 1.90 to 1.98 ppm. The protons of α -C atoms of adipic acid moiety appeared between δ 3.04 to 3.22 ppm. The protons of β -C atoms appear in the range δ 1.82 to 1.88. Aromatic protons of *o*-aminothiophenol moiety were observed as a multiplet in the range δ 6.94 to 7.92 ppm. The values are in the expected region^{33,34}. The data have been presented in Table 1.

¹³C NMR spectral data :

In addition to the carbons of parent macrocyclic complexes, the additional carbons of alkylene dithiophosphate moieties appear in the spectra. The carbons of -CH₃- group of tetramethylene, butylene and neopentylene dithiophosphate moieties appear in the range δ 13.92 to 15.22 ppm. The carbons of methylene and methine moieties appear in the range δ 41.19 to 44.32 ppm. The carbon of -CH₂- group of malonic acid moiety lie in the range δ 33.78 to 36.19 ppm. The carbons of -CH₂-CH₂- moiety appear in the range δ 28.90 to 30.69 ppm. The α -carbon of glutaric acid moiety were observed in the range δ 33.88 to 34.12 ppm and the β carbons of the above moiety appear in the range δ 28.08 to 29.06 ppm respectively. The α carbons of adipic acid moiety appeared at δ 35.04 to 36.19 ppm and β carbon at δ 28.04 to 29.32 ppm. The carbon of phthalic acid moiety observed at δ 7.62 to 7.70 ppm. Signals observed at δ 170.13 to 174.22 ppm have been assigned to the carbons of >C=O group. The signals of the carbons of -C(O)NH- group appear in the range δ 80.14 to 83.04 ppm. The carbons of phenyl group of *o*-aminothiophenol moiety appeared in the range δ 70.28 to 73.49 ppm. The values are in the expected range^{33,34}. The data have been presented in Table 2.

³¹P NMR spectral data :

³¹P NMR spectra of a few representative compounds could be recorded, however, the spectra recorded on a 270 MHz spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent and H₃PO₄ as an external standard. ³¹P NMR spectra of few representative compounds could be recorded. The chemical shift values do not show any significant change from their parent alkylene dithiophosphate acids. This indicates again the monodentate nature of alkylene dithiophosphate moieties attached to the central metal ion^{35,36}. The values of chemical shift of the newly synthesized compounds are reported in Table 3.

Structural information :

The following conclusions have been drawn from the above spectral data. The presence of four characteristic peaks for amide group in the IR spectra indicates the formation of stable macrocycles having amido group. The chemical shift values in ¹H and ¹³C NMR in the expected range, in all 14–20 membered rings, accordingly, confirms the formation of stable 14–20 membered rings. A strong band observed in the region 670–700 cm^{-1} and which, also appears in ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates, and has been attributed to free P=S moiety, indi-

Table 1. ¹H NMR spectral data of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of the macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

Sr. no.	Compd.	-CH ₃	-CH ₂ O-CHO	O -C-NH-	-CO-(CH ₂) ₂ -CO-	-CO-(CH ₂) ₃ -CO	-CO-(CH ₂) ₄ -CO	-CO-(C ₆ H ₄)-CO	Aromatic
1.	[Zn(L _{3a1})]	1.50	4.9	8.50	-	-	-	7.42	6.96
2.	[Zn(L _{2b1})]	1.56	-	8.29	3.36	-	-	-	6.94
3.	[Zn(L _{4c1})]	1.38	4.6	8.18	3.22	-	1.88	-	7.42
4.	[Zn(L _{3d1})]	1.44	3.8	8.46	-	1.98	-	-	7.36
5.	[Zn(L _{1e1})]	1.40	4.2	8.34	-	-	-	-	7.78
6.	[Cd(L _{3a2})]	1.56	4.6	8.54	-	-	-	7.59	7.90
7.	[Cd(L _{2b2})]	1.52	-	8.40	3.30	-	-	-	7.60
8.	[Cd(L _{4c2})]	1.54	4.8	8.40	3.04	-	1.82	-	7.70
9.	[Cd(L _{3d2})]	1.48	4.4	8.38	-	1.90	-	-	7.14
10.	[Cd(L _{1e2})]	1.56	4.2	8.56	-	-	-	-	7.92

Table 2. ¹³C NMR spectral data of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of the macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

Sr. no.	Compd.	-CH ₃	-CH ₂ O-CHO	>C=O	-CO-(CH ₂) ₂ -CO	-CO-(CH ₂) ₃ -CO	-CO-(CH ₂) ₄ -CO	-CO-(C ₆ H ₄)-CO	O -C-NH-	Aromatic
1.	[Zn(L _{3a1})]	14.12	41.66	170.48	-	-	-	70.70	83.04	71.12
2.	[Zn(L _{2b1})]	15.04	-	173.08	33.69	-	-	-	80.14	72.12
3.	[Zn(L _{4c1})]	13.92	42.28	171.26	35.04	-	29.32	-	82.24	73.49
4.	[Zn(L _{3d1})]	15.08	41.22	170.84	34.12	29.06	-	-	81.20	72.48
5.	[Zn(L _{1e1})]	14.58	44.32	173.26	33.78	-	-	-	81.62	70.48
6.	[Cd(L _{3a2})]	15.22	41.58	172.62	-	-	-	72.62	82.76	70.28
7.	[Cd(L _{2b2})]	14.84	-	173.06	28.90	-	-	-	82.39	70.14
8.	[Cd(L _{4c2})]	14.46	42.18	170.13	33.19	-	28.04	-	80.88	73.22
9.	[Cd(L _{3d2})]	13.98	42.02	174.22	33.88	28.08	-	-	81.40	73.22
10.	[Cd(L _{1e2})]	15.20	41.19	170.29	34.06	-	-	-	82.24	71.39

Table 3. ^{31}P NMR spectral data of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of the macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

Sr. no.	Compd. [Molecular formula]	^{31}P NMR Chemical shift (δ)
1.	$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_5\text{a}_1)]$	76.88 (73.26)
2.	$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_2\text{b}_1)]$	96.12 (93.62)
3.	$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_4\text{c}_1)]$	78.29 (74.52)
4.	$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_3\text{d}_1)]$	78.48 (74.08)
5.	$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_1\text{e}_1)]$	93.28 (95.62)
6.	$[\text{Cd}(\text{L}_5\text{a}_2)]$	79.52 (74.52)
7.	$[\text{Cd}(\text{L}_2\text{b}_2)]$	97.44 (93.62)
8.	$[\text{Cd}(\text{L}_4\text{c}_2)]$	77.10 (73.26)
9.	$[\text{Cd}(\text{L}_3\text{d}_2)]$	79.18 (74.08)
10.	$[\text{Cd}(\text{L}_1\text{e}_2)]$	95.26 (95.62)

Values of the ^{31}P chemical shifts of parent alkylene dithiophosphoric acids are given in parenthesis.

$n = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 , $(\text{CH}_2)_n = o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4^-$, $M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and Cd^{II}

Fig. 2. Mixed ligand complexes of alkylene dithiophosphate with macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} having N_2S_2 potential donor atoms in 14–20 membered ring.

cate the monodentate nature of alkylene dithiophosphate moieties. As the absorption in ^{31}P NMR doesn't show much shift from their parent alkylene dithiophosphate moieties, this also indicates the monodentate nature of the dithiophosphate ligands. Considering the above spectral data the following octahedral geometry has been assigned for these derivatives in which two sulphur atoms and two nitrogen atoms of the macrocyclic ring coordinate to the central metal ion in the square planar form and each dithiophosphate moiety occupy the axial positions binding the central metal ion in unidentate manner through strong electrostatic attraction.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antifungal activities of a few alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives have been tested against three fungi, namely *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma harzianum*. The screening data for the average percentage inhibition of the fungi at 100, 125 and 200 ppm concentrations are given in Table 4. For the sake of comparison the data of the antifungal activities of *o*-aminothiophenol, metal salts and alkylene dithiophosphoric acids have also been depicted in Table 4. The values obtained suggest that alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes are more fungitoxic than their precursor macrocyclic complexes as well as alkylene dithiophosphoric acids. Further, the data also indicate that with the increase in the concentration, the fungitoxicity also increases.

The antibacterial activity against two bacteria namely *S. typhi* and *B. subtilis* were tested by inhibition zone technique^{15,16}. The values obtained are presented in Table 4. For the sake of comparison the data of the antibacterial activities of *o*-aminothiophenol, metal salts and alkylene dithiophosphoric acids have also been depicted in Table 4. The values suggest that alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes are found to be more antibacterial than their precursor macrocyclic complexes ($M(\text{II}) \text{L}_1$ to L_5).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All of the zinc and cadmium salts and dicarboxylic acids of analytical reagent grade were obtained from s,d-fine chemicals (Mumbai, India) and were used without further purification. *o*-Aminothiophenol was used as obtained from Merck (Germany and UK). Solvent were purified and dried by standard methods.

Microanalysis for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were determined from Sophisticated Instrumentation Center for Applied Research and Testing (SICART), Vallabh Vidyanagar (India). Lead and phosphorus were estimated by standard methods²⁷.

The molecular weights were determined by Rast Camphor method. Infrared data were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Fourier (FTIR) spectrophotometer as KBr pellets. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Jeol 270 MHz spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. ³¹P NMR were recorded on the same instrument using DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent and H₃PO₄ as an external standard.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes and its derivatives :

Macrocyclic complexes were prepared by the method as reported in our earlier communication¹⁸.

Synthesis of tetramethylethylene dithiophosphate derivative of {dibenzo[7,8,15,16][6,14]diaza [1,9]dithiacyclohexadeca[2,5,10,13]tetraone} :

Macrocyclic complex mentioned above (1.822 g, 0.0033 mol) was dissolved in THF and was reacted with methanolic solution of ammonium tetramethylethylene dithiophosphate (1.518 g, 0.0066 mol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. Reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h at 90 °C. On cooling the off white crystals of dithiophosphate derivative were separated out, which were filtered through G-3 filtering funnel. Product was dried under vacuo and was crystallized with THF/C₂H₅OH mixture.

Antimicrobial studies :

The experimental part has been divided into two parts :

- (a) Evaluation of antibacterial activity and
- (b) Evaluation of antifungal activity

For present studies two bacteria have been selected viz. *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus subtilis* and three fungi viz. *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma harzianum*. *Fusarium oxysporum* is plant pathogen, causes cotton-wilt disease. The bacteria *S. typhi* is the cause of enteric fever (typhoid) and *B. subtilis* may on occasion act as an opportunistic pathogen causing eye infection and septicemia.

(a) Evaluation of antibacterial activity :

In the present work, activities of the some synthesized compounds have been evaluated by standard filter paper disc method. The aim of these investigation was to study the changes in the activity with the variation in the structure of the molecule and thereby to draw some inferences

whether the structure of the compound may have some correlations with antibacterial activity.

All the synthesized compounds have been screened *in vitro* against the following two bacteria. Here streptomycin is used as a standard/control.

- (a) *Salmonella typhi*
- (b) *Bacillus subtilis*

In the present work the medium has the following composition :

Meat extract	- 100 ml
Peptone	- 1.0 g
Sodium chloride	- 0.5 g

Fig. 3. Culture of antifungal activity.

Fig. 4. Culture of antibacterial activity.

For the preparation of meat extract, 500 g of fat free minced meat was placed in 1000 ml of distilled water for 24 h in cold. The mixture was strained through a muslin cloth. The residue was discarded and the obtained filtrate had red colour. The surface fat was removed by skimming with filter paper and it was boiled for 15 min. The insoluble proteins became coagulated. The fluid was fil-

Table 4. Antimicrobial activity of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of the macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}

^aAntifungal activity - Average % of inhibition after 72 h at 30 ± 2 °C.

^bAntibacterial activity - Average % growth inhibition after 4 h at 30 ± 2 °C (conc. in ppm).

Sr. no.	Compd.	^a <i>Aspergillus flavus</i>			^a <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>			^a <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>			^b <i>B. subtilis</i>		^b <i>S. typhi</i>	
		100	125	200	100	125	200	100	125	200	100	125	100	125
(a)	Bavistin (standard)	98	97	99	96	98	99	97	98	99	98	99	97	99
(b)	<i>o</i> -Aminothiophenol	32	32	40	34	39	41	33	38	42	11	13	10	14
(c)	ZnCl ₂	21	34	42	23	37	44	22	36	40	9	11	10	12
(d)	ZnBr ₂	22	34	38	21	37	40	21	36	40	10	13	10	13
(e)	Zn(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	23	36	44	25	36	41	23	37	41	10	13	11	14
(f)	Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	21	32	40	21	38	42	22	30	40	9	12	10	13
(g)	CdCl ₂	30	38	42	32	36	42	31	37	41	11	14	9	12
(h)	CdBr ₂	31	38	41	33	37	42	30	36	40	13	17	14	18
(i)	Cd(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	32	39	42	31	40	44	30	37	41	14	16	13	15
(j)	HOOC-CH ₂ -COOH	16	20	24	17	31	26	21	26	29	5	7	66	9
(k)	HOOC-(CH ₂) ₂ -COOH	20	24	26	22	27	29	24	27	30	8	10	8	11
(l)	HOOC-(CH ₂) ₃ -COOH	21	23	27	22	27	30	21	25	28	6	4	7	9
(m)	HOOC-(CH ₂) ₄ -COOH	20	24	29	21	25	29	24	27	29	7	9	6	8
(n)	HOOC-C ₆ H ₄ -COOH	21	24	27	20	24	28	20	26	30	7	11	9	11
(o)	Ha	61	65	66	62	66	70	63	67	72	31	34	30	33
(p)	Hb	62	67	70	66	69	71	62	65	68	30	33	28	32
(q)	Hc	63	67	69	64	70	75	60	65	71	30	34	28	35
(r)	Hd	60	65	70	61	66	71	62	66	72	29	35	27	34
(s)	He	60	65	68	61	66	70	60	66	62	27	31	27	32
1.	[Zn(L _{5a} 1)]	63	67	71	60	66	71	60	66	70	32	41	30	41
2.	[Zn(L _{2b} 1)]	63	68	72	61	67	71	61	67	72	30	37	31	40
3.	[Zn(L _{4c} 1)]	60	66	71	61	67	72	61	66	71	41	31	31	40
4.	[Zn(L _{3d} 1)]	61	67	70	62	68	72	60	66	70	31	38	32	40
5.	[Zn(L _{1e} 1)]	62	67	71	61	66	70	61	66	70	27	35	28	35
6.	[Cd(L _{4a} 2)]	68	74	79	67	74	80	69	75	80	39	46	37	45
7.	[Cd(L _{2b} 2)]	66	70	78	65	72	76	66	73	77	35	40	36	42
8.	[Cd(L _{5c} 2)]	67	70	72	67	72	79	66	71	79	38	42	39	44
9.	[Cd(L _{3d} 2)]	67	71	77	66	71	78	65	71	78	37	43	38	45
10.	[Cd(L _{1e} 2)]	65	70	78	62	71	77	65	72	76	40	45	41	48

tered through cheesecloth and its volume was raised up to the original volume with the addition of distilled water. This made the extract clear yellow in colour.

Nutrient broth :

All the ingredients-peptone (1 g), sodium chloride (500 mg) and meat extract (100 ml) were mixed and heated till they dissolved. Then it was filtered through a filter paper by adjusting the pH at 7.4 by using normal sodium hydroxide solution. The medium so obtained was poured into the sterile flask and plugged with sterile cotton plug which was then sterilized in a autoclave 15 lb pressure for 15 min.

Nutrient agar :

Agar is a complex carbohydrate, obtained from certain marine algae and is used as a solidifying agent for media. It is not considered as a source of nutrition for the bacteria. It has the following composition.

- Agar power - 20 g
- Nutrient broth - 100 ml

The above mixture was boiled in running steam till agar particles dissolved completely (for about half an hour). It was then filtered through a glass wool in hot medium (pH adjusted at 7.4). Then the medium was kept in the

Fig. 5. Antifungal activity – average % of inhibition after 72 h at 30 ± 2 °C.

Fig. 6. Antibacterial activity – average % growth inhibition after 24 h at 30 ± 2 °C (conc. in ppm).

flask and heated in an autoclave at 15 lb pressure for 15 min. Finally, it was transferred into the sterilized petridishes.

Inoculation of test plates :

At least four or five well-isolated colonies having the same morphological type were selected from an agar plate culture with a wire loop. The top of each colony was touched and transferred the growth to a tube containing 4 to 5 ml of suitable broth medium. The broth culture was incubated at 37 °C for 8 h. The sterile cotton swab on woolen application was dipped into the inoculum. The excess of inoculum was removed from the swab by rotating (several times) inside the wall of the test tube above the final level. The dried surface of a Miller Hinto agar plate was inoculated by streaking the swab over the entire sterile agar surface. The streaking was repeated two or three times so as to ensure an even distribution of the inoculum

Application of disc :

Within about 15 min, after the inoculation of plates; antimicrobial impregnated discs were applied on the surface of the inoculated plates with sterile forceps. Aseptically, each disc was pressed on the medium to ensure complete contact. The spatial arrangement of the discs must be such that they are not close from the edges of the plate and far enough apart to prevent overlapping of the zones of inhibition. Since some diffusion of test compound is almost instantaneous, a disc was not moved once it came in contact with agar surface.

Incubation of test plate :

The individual plates were evenly dispersed on the incubator shelf (at 37 °C) so as to make each plate reached approximately to incubator temperature for some time.

Reading and interpretation :

After 24 h of incubation, the plates were examined and the diameter of the zones of complete inhibition was measured to the nearest whole millimeter with a sliding calipers.

(b) Evaluation of antifungal activity :

There are several methods available for recording the antifungal activity of compounds. The one, which is in common use in the recent time, has been adopted.

Some of the synthesized compounds have been screened

for their *in vitro* antifungal activity against the following three fungi using Griseofulvin as a standard.

(a) *Aspergillus flavus*

(b) *Fusarium oxysporum*

(c) *Trichoderma harzianum*

Sterilization of the apparatus :

All the glass apparatus were cleaned with chromic acid followed by distilled water and sterilized by heating at 2000 °C in a hot air oven.

Preparation of the medium :

Sabourauds dextrose agar medium, was used for antifungal screening which consists of :

Dextrose	- 20 g
Potato	- 200 g
Agar	- 20 g
Distilled water	- 1000 ml
Streptomycin	- 0.2 g

Streptomycin was used to check the growth of undesirable bacteria. The above mentioned ingredients were weighted and dissolved in a 500 ml of distilled water. When the ingredients were dissolved completely, more distilled water was added to make the solution up to one liter and pH of the medium was kept at 7.4 ± 0.1 . The medium was heated in an autoclave at 15 lb pressure for half an hour and then transferred into the sterilized petridishes. The broth has been prepared in 1000 ml by using dextrose and peptone.

The spore suspension of each test organism (72 h autoclave) was kept in a broth at 35–45 °C. The petridishes were inoculated in the same manner as described earlier for antibacterial screening. These petridishes were incubated at 30 °C for 48 h. The zone of inhibition was considered as an indication for the antifungal activity.

References

1. R. M Izatt and J. J. Christensen, "Synthesis of Selective Agents", John Wiley, New York, 1987.
2. Y. Inoue and G. W. Gokel (eds.), "Cation Binding by Macrocycles", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1990.
3. P. Guerriero, S. Tamburini and P. A. Vigato, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **139**, 17.
4. A. T. Yordanov and D. M. Roundhill, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **170**, 93.

5. C. P. Bhasin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **131**, 77.
6. H. P. S. Chauhan, C. P. Bhasin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon and the Related Elements*, 1983, **15**.
7. C. P. Bhasin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **128**, 69.
8. C. P. Bhasin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 834.
9. C. P. Bhasin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **131**, 195.
10. C. P. Bhasin, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **144**, 157.
11. C. P. Bhasin, R. Bohra, G. Srivastava, R. C. Mehrotra and P. B. Hitchcock, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **164**, 11.
12. C. P. Bhasin, R. S. Dave and K. A. Parmar, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2001, **2**, 26.
13. C. P. Bhasin, R. S. Dave and K. A. Parmar, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2001, **2**, 52.
14. C. P. Bhasin and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 336.
15. C. P. Bhasin and D. G. Panchal, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem. and Nano Met. Chem.*, 2005, **35**, 213.
16. C. P. Bhasin and D. G. Panchal, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon and the Related Elements*, 2004, **179**, 1545.
17. C. P. Bhasin, A. G. Gupta and M. P. Gongiwala, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 1073.
18. C. P. Bhasin, J. P. Patel and M. L. Desai, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon and the Related Elements*, 2008, **183**, 2015.
19. C. P. Bhasin, K. V. Goswami and M. P. Gongiwala, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2009, **26**, 12.
20. C. P. Bhasin and M. L. Desai, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2009, **26**, 113.
21. D. G. Panchal, PhD Thesis, Hem. North Gujarat University, 2005.
22. A. G. Gupta, PhD Thesis, Hem. North Gujarat University, 2006.
23. M. P. Gongiwala, PhD Thesis, Hem. North Gujarat University, 2006.
24. M. L. Desai, PhD Thesis, Hem. North Gujarat University, 2007.
25. J. P. Patel, PhD Thesis, Hem. North Gujarat University, 2007.
26. V. M. Patel, PhD Thesis, Hem. North Gujarat University, 2008.
27. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", 5th ed., Longman, London, 1999.
28. M. Shakir and S. P. Varkey, *Polyhedron*, 1995, **14**, 1117.
29. D. E. C. Corbridge, M. Grayson and E. J. Griffith (eds.), "Topics in Phosphorous Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1969, **6**, 235.
30. J. Cason, W. N. Baxter and W. DeAcetis, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 247.
31. R. A. Y. Jones and A. R. Katritzky, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 4376.
32. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds Part B : Application in Coordination Organometallic and Bioinorganic Chemistry", 5th ed., Wiley Interscience, New York, 1997, 65.
33. R. M. Silverstein and F. X. Webster, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., 1998.
34. J. B. Lambert, H. S. Shurvell, D. A. Lightner and R. G. Cooks, "Organic Structural Spectroscopy", Prentice Hall, 1998.
35. H. P. S. Chauhan, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **173**, 1.
36. H. P. S. Chauhan, "The Chemistry an Application of Alkoxy, Aryloxy and Applied Derivatives of Elements", RBSA Publishers, Jaipur, India, 2003, 339.